

CHILDREN'S FICTION LITERATURE IS AN INEXHAUSTIBLE RICHNESS OF THE NATIVE LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The article examines the importance of introducing children to fiction literature in the formation of communicative abilities, particularly in the development of speech.

Key words: the native language, the method of communication, poetic speech, fiction literature;

The successful implementation of the State Curriculum “Ilk qadam” and its objectives depends on a number of factors, and above all on the way life is organized in a preschool institution, as well as the atmosphere in which all necessary conditions for the educational and upbringing process are created.

The effectiveness of education and instruction is achieved through the diligent work of teachers who work directly with children, as well as all staff members of the preschool institution who interact with preschoolers throughout the day.

Mastering the native language as a means and method of communication and cognition is one of the most important achievements of a child in preschool age. An important role in the development of speech and the enrichment of a child’s vocabulary is played by fiction literature.

Children enjoy listening to folktales, poems, and stories. Children’s literature primarily brings them joy through its engaging content, the beauty of artistic images, expressive language, and the musicality of poetic speech. At the same time, it also has an educational influence on children. In particular, realistic stories, fairy tales, and poems serve for young children as a form of understanding the surrounding reality, teaching them to think, feel, and comprehend.

Every day, a child’s vocabulary and personal experience expand through direct observation and perception. Artistic language helps the child clarify and consolidate knowledge, gradually enriching it with new concepts and ideas.

Fiction opens up and explains to the child the life of society and nature, and the world of human feelings and relationships. It develops the child’s thinking and imagination, enriches their emotions, and provides excellent models of the native literary language.

Children’s fiction literature can be regarded as a primary source of upbringing, containing significant educational and developmental potential.

Fiction literature contributes to the development of a child’s thinking, imagination, and speech, enriches the child’s emotional world, and fosters love for the Motherland and its nature.

Modern children are more interested in smartphones, computers, and video games than in reading books. The practice of family reading has almost disappeared, and it is children who suffer from this the most. Children’s interest in books has declined; they rarely visit libraries. First and foremost, parents should reflect on this problem. Adults need to understand the importance of fiction literature in shaping a child’s personality. From early childhood, parents can introduce a child to books, tell fairy tales, read poems aloud, and show vivid illustrations. It

is important to take the child's interests into account and choose literature together with them. Most importantly, it is essential to discuss what has been read with the child. In addition, adults should strive to master the art of expressive reading, especially when reading for children.

Literary language is perceived through reading and listening. In the first case, perception is direct; in the second, it is mediated through a performer—the reader or storyteller – who acts as an intermediary between the author and the listener. The reader-performer, using variations in voice and other means of expressive speech, brings the literary work to life and gives it an appropriate sound pattern. The work of the reader is a responsible one both to the author and to the audience. By performing a literary work, the reader conveys the author's thoughts and feelings. The reader's task is to help listeners visualize what they hear, to make images and scenes vivid and realistic, and to evoke specific emotions and experiences.

As a result, a child develops the ability to express thoughts in a coherent and grammatically correct manner. During listening and discussion, the child's memory develops, along with emotional responses toward literary characters. In the future, such children grow into spiritually and intellectually developed individuals with a well-formed personality. Fiction literature serves as a powerful and effective means of intellectual, moral, and aesthetic education of children. It also has a profound influence on the development and enrichment of a child's speech.

Therefore, in order to promote reading, the Culture and Arts Development Foundation of Uzbekistan organized a free bus service for students of general education schools in Tashkent to visit the Republican Children's Library. The lilac-colored bus is decorated with the inscription: "Men Respublika bolalar kutubxonasi ketyapman" – "I am going to the Republican Children's Library."

It is necessary to introduce children to the world of fiction from an early age; otherwise, it may be too late, as with growing up children lose the sharpness of word perception and the ability to admire the beauty and wonder of human speech. If a preschool child does not realize that reading a good book is interesting, then at school, sitting with textbooks and computers, they may never develop a love for fiction literature.

The world of reading helps adults enrich and guide children's imagination. It is on the pages of books that children encounter, for the first time, a harmonious reflection of reality. Books speak about the most important and beautiful things, which is why children cannot help but love them—they are always happy to meet them.

Thus, children's literary works reveal to children the inexhaustible richness of their native language, helping them begin to use this richness in everyday speech communication and in their own creative verbal expression.

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